

Dyes Derived from Substituted Phthalic Acids. Part V. 3,6-Endoxohexahydrophthalic Acid. Effect of Completely Saturating and also of Introducing an Oxygen Bridge in the Phthalic Acid Portion of Phthalein Dyes

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3,6-Endoxohexahydrophthalic acid, in the form of its anhydride, has been condensed with a number of aromatic hydroxy (phenols) and hydroxyamino (*m*-diethylaminophenol) compounds. The phthalein and rhodamine types of compounds have been studied analytically and spectrophotometrically and compared with similar compounds obtained from phthalic acid. The resorcinol compound has also been brominated and acetylated. The effect of completely saturating and introducing an oxygen bridge in the phthalic acid portion of phthalein dyes has been studied.

3,6-Endoxohexahydrophthalic anhydride (I), prepared from 3,6-endoxotetrahydrophthalic anhydride by hydrogenation¹, has been condensed with several phenols under different conditions to obtain phthalein and rhodamine types of dyes. The resorcinol compound has been brominated and acetylated. The phthaleins, thus prepared, have been studied spectrophotometrically and the absorption maxima compared with those of phthaleins and rhodamines from phthalic anhydride.

(I)

The phthaleins and rhodamines obtained are of the following types:

- II : R¹ = R² = R⁴ = H; R³ = -OH.
 III : R¹ = -Me; R² = R⁴ = H; R³ = -OH.
 IV : R¹ = R³ = -OH; R² = R⁴ = H.
 V : R¹ = R² = R⁴ = H; R³ = -NEt₂.
 VI : R¹ = H; R² = R⁴ = Br; R³ = -OH.
 VII : R¹ = R² = R⁴ = H; R³ = -OCOMe.

- VIII : R¹ = -OH; R² = H.
 IX : R¹ = -OH; R² = -Me.

EXPERIMENTAL

Powdered maleic anhydride (19.6 g.) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was added to dry and freshly distilled furan (14.05 g.); the mixture was shaken for 30 to 40 minutes and kept aside at room temperature for 6 hours. 3,6-Endoxotetrahydrophthalic anhydride (m.p. 123-24°), thus obtained, was hydrogenated in acetone medium to obtain crystals of 3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalic anhydride¹ (I), m.p. 115-16°. The preparation of phthaleins and rhodamines, given below, were carried out using the anhydride (I) in presence of a few drops of H₂SO₄ (conc.) by methods described earlier^{2,3}.

Resorcinol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (II) was obtained by condensation of a mixture of anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and resorcinol (2.3 g.) at 160-80° for 3 hours.

Orcinol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (III) was obtained similarly from a mixture of the anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and orcinol (2.5 g.) by heating at 150-70° for 4 hours.

Phloroglucinol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (IV) was obtained by heating a mixture of the anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and phloroglucinol (2.55 g.) at 180-200° for 3 hours.

m-Diethylaminophenol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (V) was obtained by condensation of a mixture of the anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and *m*-diethylaminophenol (2.35 g.) at 180-200° for 3 hours.

Tetrabromoresorcinol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (VI) was obtained by brominating compound (II) by the method of Baeyer⁴.

Resorcinol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein diacetate (VII) was obtained by acetylating compound (II) with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate.

Phenol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (VIII) was obtained by heating a mixture of the anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and phenol (3.0 g.) at 110-15° for 20 hours. The excess of phenol was removed from the phthalein by steam distillation.

o-Cresol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalein (IX).—The cresolphthalein was obtained by heating a mixture of the anhydride (I; 1.68 g.) and *o*-cresol (3.5 g.) at 115-2° for 14 hours.

The characteristic properties and analytical data of the above compounds are recorded in Table I.

Light absorption ($\lambda_{\max}$) of the compounds prepared were determined by using "Hilger Uvispek" spectrophotometer and were found of similar nature in the two systems. The maxima for phthalein type of compounds were taken in neutral and alkaline (a drop of 5% NaOH) ethanolic solutions (Table II) and $\lambda_{\max}$ for the rhodamine type of compounds were determined in neutral and acidic (a drop of 5*N*-HCl) ethanolic solutions (Table III). The $\lambda_{\max}$ for phthaleins and rhodamines from phthalic anhydride were also determined under similar conditions.

2. Loival and Jain, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 251.

3. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1962, 39, 385.

4. Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1876, 183, 3.

TABLE I

Dyes.	M.P. (d)	Cryst. appearance.	C o l o u r i n		Formula.	Found	Reqd.
			EtOH soln.	Alk-EtOH soln.			
II	>300°	Dark brown	*Wine red	*Pink	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	C : 67.90% H : 4.56	68.18% 4.55
III	225°	Brown	Orange-yellow	Wine-red	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	C : 69.10 H : 5.28	69.47 5.26
IV	>300°	Dark brown	Yellow	Blood-red	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	C : 62.20 H : 4.19	62.50 4.17
V	>300°	Pink	Pink	†Intense pink	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ O ₄ N ₂	C : 72.50 H : 7.38 N : 6.04	72.73 7.38 6.06
VI	>300°	Red brown	Blood-red	Deep pink	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ O ₆ Br ₄	Br : 47.80	47.90
VII	220°	Pinkish	Yellowish	Yellowish	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₆	C : 65.80 H : 4.60	66.06 4.59
VIII	225°	Brown	Yellow	Light pink	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅	C : 70.80 H : 5.34	71.00 5.33
IX	210°	„	„	Purple-pink	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 72.02 H : 6.04	72.13 6.01

*With green fluorescence
(d) decomposes.
†In acidic EtOH Soln.

TABLE II

Phenols.	P h t h a l e i n s i n		3,6-Endoxohexahydrophthalic in	
	Neutral EtOH soln.	Alkaline EtOH soln.	Neutral EtOH soln.	Alkaline EtOH soln.
Resorcinol	450 m μ	490 m μ	490 m μ	496 m μ
Orcinol	445	490	440	505
Phloroglucinol	440	460	410	440
Tetrabromoresorcinol	525	515	515	515
Phenol	..	545	..	520
o-Cresol	..	560	..	540

TABLE III

From phthalic anhydride.		From 3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalic anhydride.	
<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenolphthalein (Rhodamine B)		<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenol-3,6-endoxohexahydrophthalic.	
Neutral EtOH soln.	Acidic EtOH soln.	Neutral EtOH soln.	Acidic EtOH soln.
535 m μ	545 m μ	520 m μ	530 m μ

DISCUSSION

A comparative study of the absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max}$) of the dyestuffs shows that the changes in the lower portion of the phthalein dyes (completely saturating and also introducing an oxygen bridge in the phthalic acid portion) have no appreciable effect on the light absorption, except in the case of phloroglucinol, phenol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethylaminophenol compounds (vide Tables II and III).

The lower values of absorption maxima in case of phloroglucinol, phenol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethylaminophenol compounds of anhydride (I) are probably due to the complete saturation of the phthalic acid portion, which has completely destroyed the conjugation between the upper and lower portions of the phthalein molecules, as illustrated below in case of phenol and *m*-diethylaminophenol compounds of phthalic acid and of anhydride (I).

Phenolphthalein.

Phenol compound from anhydride (I).

Rhodamine B.

m-Diethylaminophenol compound from anhydride (I).

In cases of resorcinol, orcinol, and tetrabromoresorcinol compounds, the variation in $\lambda_{\max}$ is insignificant. This fact again refutes the effect of complete saturation, oxygen bridge, and bicyclic nature of the phthalic acid portion in lowering the absorption maxima.

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